

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Misperceptions and Demand for Democracy under Authoritarianism"

Korhan Kocak¹ Evaluator 2 Bob Kubinec

¹NYU Abu Dhabi

Published on: Aug 07, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.ef6f66cd>

License: [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: “Misperceptions and Demand for Democracy under Authoritarianism”^[1]. This research involved ambitious field (and online) experiments into the impact of providing information on “the status and implications of democracy and media freedom on actual beliefs and voting patterns in Türkiye”, yielding encouraging, actionable results. Both evaluations are strongly positive about the research contribution and overall rigor. Both offer substantive suggestions (as does the evaluation manager Bob Kubinec, below). Evaluator 1 (Korhan Kocak) raised some concerns with the use of post-treatment values as outcomes given ex-ante group differences. They also requested a “robust discussion of the studies’ ethics”. The second (anonymous) evaluator raised concerns about the reliability of the V-Dem indicators data; about the construct validity – mismanagement and corruption vs. democracy and freedom; and about interpreting the estimates given substantial heterogeneity in compliance. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Korhan Kocak](#)
2. [Evaluator 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Korhan Kocak	85	4.1
Evaluator 2	88	4.3

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Korhan Kocak

Why authoritarian leaders continue to receive support despite openly agitating against democratic institutions is one of the most important puzzles of the last few decades. This paper argues that the answer is partly lack of knowledge about the costs of authoritarianism. Using an online and a field experiment, the authors show that informational treatments that remedy this lack of knowledge can have substantial effects on both beliefs and voting behavior.

Anonymous Evaluator 2

This paper makes a valuable contribution to research on authoritarianism and democratic resilience by combining an online survey and a large-scale field experiment in Turkey to test whether correcting factual misperceptions about institutional decline can shift political attitudes and electoral behavior.

The study is theoretically ambitious, well-powered, and methodologically transparent, with the field experiment demonstrating real-world behavioral effects on opposition vote share. The paper could be improved by addressing the mismatch between the authors' normative framing of democracy and media freedom and the more instrumental, performance-based content of their treatments. The authors could also do more to address concerns about treatment spillover and compliance heterogeneity in the field experiment.

Overall, the study is rigorous and policy-relevant, and it offers a strong foundation for future work on information-based interventions in hybrid regimes.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2		
	Korhan Kocak			Anonymous		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	85	(70, 95)		88	(80, 95)	

Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	90	(80, 94)		83	(75, 90)	6
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	90	(75, 95)		88	(80, 95)	
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁸	75	(60, 90)		88	(80, 95)	
Logic & communication 9	90	(80, 95)		88	(80, 95)	
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁰	30* ¹¹	(15, 50)	12	83	(75, 90)	
Real-world relevance 13 , 14	90	(80, 95)		88	(80, 95)	
Relevance to global priorities ¹⁵ , ¹⁶	90	(80, 95)		88	(80, 95)	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Korhan Kocak		Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI

On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.1	(3.4, 4.4)	4.3	(3.5, 5.0)
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	4.3	(3.0, 4.7)	4.3	(3.5, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ¹⁷	Belief in claim ¹⁸	Suggested robustness checks ¹⁹	Important 'implication', policy, credibility ²⁰
Evaluator 1 Korhan Kocak	Voters' support for authoritarian regimes comes in part from their lack of knowledge about the costs of authoritarianism. Informational interventions that remedy this can have a substantial impact on vote shares (to the tune of 2.4 pp).	I strongly believe it.	The outcome measure should not be post-treatment means but the difference between pre-treatment and post-treatment. Otherwise, I think there are sufficient robustness checks.	Small changes in their messaging (i.e. talking about scientific consensus on the importance of press freedom and other democratic institutions) can dramatically improve their effectiveness... at little to no additional cost.

<p>Evaluator 2 Anonymous</p>	<p>Exposure to nonpartisan, factual messages about institutional decline led to a measurable increase in opposition vote share in the 2023 Turkish presidential election. Treated neighborhoods experienced a 2.4 percentage point increase... a 4.4% increase relative to baseline support levels.</p>	<p>The field experiment is well-powered, pre-registered, and analyzed using appropriate instrumental variable (2SLS) methods. Somewhat cautious due to 1) potential spillover across adjacent neighborhoods; 2) variation in treatment compliance and delivery success; 3) uncertainty about the underlying mechanism</p>	<p>Conducting spatial spillover checks would help validate the localized nature of the treatment effect. Presenting CACE estimates would clarify treatment effects among those who received the intervention.</p>	<p>Nonpartisan, factual messaging about institutional decline can meaningfully shift electoral outcomes even under authoritarian or hybrid regimes. Generalizability may be limited... [and] likely depends on contextual factors.</p>
---	---	---	---	--

Evaluation manager's discussion

It is a pleasure to write a summary for the ambitious new working paper on misinformation in elections under authoritarianism by Acemoglu et al [2]. As our evaluators noted, the research design was robust, creative, and implemented during a critical period in Turkish politics. Employing both an online survey experiment and a confederate field experiment with actual Turkish political parties, the authors were able to test for the effect of their messages about the state of Turkish political institutions on a wide array of attitudes and electoral behavior. In short, the intervention worked, both in terms of changing Turkish voters' perceptions of Turkish democracy and even their choice in the ballot box. As the authors report, the opposition vote share experienced a remarkable +0.8pp vote share increase at the neighborhood/precinct level, and when the proportion treated is taken into account, is perhaps even higher at approximately +2pp (2SLS estimates in the appendix). Given that the treatment was purely informational—it did not involve longer-term contact or focus groups—this is a truly remarkable result.

Political scientists have long theorized that control over information plays a critical role in sustaining and enabling authoritarian government. Especially in a world in which people almost always report a preference for democracy, for a regime to maintain a monopoly on competition, it needs to justify restrictions on democratic practice through misdirection of some sort. However, while we have excellent theoretical treatments [3][4], and careful on-the-ground field research [5], it is very tricky to directly manipulate the information people receive—in part because only people who are already *opposed* to the authoritarian regime are interested in hearing counter-regime messaging [6].

For example, Metaketa I, arguably the most ambitious effort to test the effect of information provision to voters by running the same study in five countries, found a treatment effect of almost perfectly zero for information provided to voters about incumbent performance [7].²¹ In an even more ominous study, [8] found that an anti-corruption message *encouraged*, rather than discouraged, a preference among voters for tolerating corrupt politicians. The problem, of course, is that much can be lost between the transmission of information and its reception. Especially in a political context, people are naturally suspicious of freely-provided information as it is hard to be truly non-partisan when information may hurt or help one political side.

For these reasons, the evaluators—and myself—are thrilled to see some strong and positive effects of information about Turkey’s democratic decline on support for authoritarianism. Furthermore, we know that these effects are concentrated among people who were government supporters whether in the online experiment (Figure A-10) or in the field experiment (Figure 7). These are the type of heterogeneous relationships that we would want to see if the information theory of authoritarian government is true. If authoritarian leaders like Turkish President Tayyip Erdogan are successfully manipulating the information environment to secure support, then an intervention that provides credible information about the health of democracy should have a stronger effect on people who were more receptive to Erdogan’s messages.

This is certainly good news, but of course we need to frame this result within our broader context of scientific knowledge. At The Unjournal, we particularly want to know whether interventions will travel well to new situations. In this case, it will be difficult to know for sure. The reason is, as Evaluator 2 notes, that there are a lot of different attributes both of the treatment and the political environment that are relatively unique. Figure A-3 shows what the pamphlets that were distributed with political parties looked like, which as Evaluator 2 points out, represent specific information about “media neutrality and independence.” While media freedom is a core part of democracy, there are of course many other attributes of democracy the research team could have emphasized. The authors of the study also used an impartiality framing in which they tried to emphasize the scientific nature of their information about media quality, which was drawn from the [Varieties of Democracy](#) project. It could be that this scientific framing is what gave the intervention so much efficacy—but we would not be able to know this without further testing.

Second, it is important to emphasize that the effect of the treatment is conditional on aspects both of the general political environment and specific local institutions. While Turkey has become quite authoritarian in recent years, it still has a relatively healthy civil society and level of political debate compared to say the United Arab Emirates or China. Furthermore, President Erdogan was seen as uniquely vulnerable after more than a decade in office and a declining economy, which may have made his voters more receptive to messages criticizing him. As Evaluator 1 mentioned regarding so-called “spillover” effects, even the electoral geography can affect the treatment efficacy depending on the distribution of government vs. opposition supporters in particular neighborhoods.

For these reasons, we urge the authors to consider doing more work to theorize as to what it was that made their intervention so successful, especially when compared to other experimental attempts that were unsuccessful. Isolating different components of the treatment and understanding how they affect voter perceptions is crucial for building foundational knowledge in this field and designing interventions for real-world use.

In addition, it is important to note that there are a number of statistical choices that have to be made when analyzing what is a fairly complex experiment. Our evaluators pointed out that they could consider alternative strategies for estimating the treatment effect of the field experiment, whether examining the complier-average causal effect (CACE) from evaluator 2 or “persuasion effects” from evaluator 1. Understandably, there are a number of possible statistical analyses that could be done with this data, and we do encourage the authors to pursue alternative estimands so we can maximize what we can learn from this study.

I would add to this discussion that it is important to note that the field experiment’s power depends strongly on including the value of the prior election in the regression analyses. In Table 2 columns 1-2, the standard error declines by half when the prior election result is included in the intention-to-treat (ITT) estimate for the field experiment. Without including it, the estimate is too noisy to be considered “statistically significant.” This particular issue should not be considered a major limitation, however, as conditioning on the prior value of the outcome is considered best practice when analyzing experiments.

At the same time, it is important to note that the field experiment is necessarily more limited in terms of power than the online experiment, which has a massive treatment size of over 4,000 subjects. For these reasons, it may be difficult to perform more complicated re-analysis of the field experiment results such as spatial analysis as evaluator 1 recommends. Given that the treatment effects are relatively consistent across different types of elections, though, it would appear that the field experiment effect is fairly robust even given the limitations in power. The authors might consider using the (ordered) beta regression estimator to maximize power given that the outcome is bounded and thus non-linear [9][10].

Unjournal process notes

Note on versions (see footnote)²²

How we chose the evaluators

We looked for evaluators with expertise and research experience involving political economy, electoral behavior, misperceptions and information, experiments (online and field), and causal inference econometrics, as well as familiarity with the field context. Although it was challenging to find researchers with this expertise who had not worked with the authors (especially given Acemoglu’s prolificacy), evaluator reported a conflict of interest.

Author engagement

The authors were aware of our this evaluation and kept us up-to-date on the most recent versions of their work. We invited them to provide a reply, but Ceren Baysan noted “I’m unsure when we’d be able to write a response.” As always, if they are able to provide a response, we will integrate it into this package.

References

[1] Acemoglu, D., Aksoy, C. G., Baysan, C., Molina, C., & Zeki, G. (2024). *Misperceptions and Demand for Democracy under Authoritarianism*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w33018>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)

2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)

3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5. “Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?”

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

6. While the evidence is credible, the authors’ claims regarding “demand for democracy” are quite broad and normative despite the narrower more instrumental nature of their treatments. [↵](#)

7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

8. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

9. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

10.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

11. Manager: The discussion suggests that this is a provisional rating subject to change. We aim to ask the evaluator to clarify this. [↵](#)

12. Presumably, the authors will make replication code and data available once they publish this paper [↵](#)

13.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↵](#)

14.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

15. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

16.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↔](#)

17.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↔](#)

18. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you **believe** the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↔](#)

19.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↔](#)

20.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important *implication* of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you *believe* this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

⇐

21. For a visualization of their treatment findings, see their Shiny app available at https://egap.shinyapps.io/metaketa_shiny/. ⇐

22. We had some miscommunication with the evaluators, and they each seem to have considered the October 2024 version, at least in part, instead of the March 2025 version. We followed up with both evaluators, highlighting some of the things that had changed between the versions, although the differences were not generally major. Other than updating the precise numbers referred to, the evaluators declined to update their reports. One of the evaluators noted "I don't think these changes substantively impact the rest of my comments." Our own take is the same: the updates do not substantially interact with the evaluations. ⇐

References

1. Acemoglu, Daron, Cevat Giray Aksoy, Ceren Baysan, Carlos Molina, and Gamze Zeki. 2024. 'Misperceptions and Demand for Democracy under Authoritarianism'. Working Paper. Working Paper Series. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w33018>. ⇐
2. Acemoglu, D., Aksoy, C. G., Baysan, C., Molina, C., & Zeki, G. (2024). Misperceptions and demand for democracy under authoritarianism. *National Bureau of Economic Research*. ⇐
3. Little, A. T., Schnakenberg, K. E., & Turner, I. R. (2022). Motivated reasoning and democratic accountability. *American Political Science Review*, 116(2), 751767. Retrieved from <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-political-science-review/article/motivated-reasoning-and-democratic-accountability/A5FDC6F7175255BDE8AA6AC054CD9176> ⇐
4. Little, A. T. (2017). Propaganda and credulity. *Games and Economic Behavior*, 102, 224232. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0899825616301476> ⇐

5. Letsa, N. W. (2025). *The autocratic voter: Partisanship and political socialization under dictatorship*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. [↵](#)
6. Batista Pereira, F., Bueno, N. S., Nunes, F., & Pavão, N. (2022). Fake news, fact checking, and partisanship: The resilience of rumors in the 2018 Brazilian elections. *The Journal of Politics*, 84(4), 2188–2201. Retrieved from <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/full/10.1086/719419> [↵](#)
7. Dunning, T., Grossman, G., Humphreys, M., Hyde, S. D., McIntosh, C., & Nellis, G. (2019). *Information, accountability, and cumulative learning: Lessons from metaketa i*. Cambridge University Press. [↵](#)
8. Cheeseman, N., & Peiffer, C. (2021). The Curse of Good Intentions: Why Anticorruption Messaging Can Encourage Bribery. *American Political Science Review*, 1–15. Retrieved from <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-political-science-review/article/curse-of-good-intentions-why-anticorruption-messaging-can-encourage-bribery/CE180F511D68B5A4D14904ACFA3728F4> [↵](#)
9. Smithson, M., & Verkuilen, J. (2006). A better lemon squeezer? Maximum-likelihood regression with beta-distributed independent variables. *Psychological Methods*, 11(1), 54–71. [↵](#)
10. Kubinec, R. (2022). Ordered Beta Regression: A Parsimonious, Well-Fitting Model for Continuous Data with Lower and Upper Bounds. *Political Analysis*, 1–18. Retrieved from <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/political-analysis/article/ordered-beta-regression-a-parsimonious-wellfitting-model-for-continuous-data-with-lower-and-upper-bounds/89F4141DA16D4FC217809B5EB45EEE83> [↵](#)
11. Acemoglu, D., Aksoy, C. G., Baysan, C., Molina, C., & Zeki, G. (2024). *Misperceptions and Demand for Democracy under Authoritarianism*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w33018> [↵](#)